

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ORGANIZING DIAGNOSTICS OF FORMATION OF FUTURE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS' INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ADAM MICKIEWICZ UNIVERSITY OF POLAND

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Abstract

The article discusses about the importance and content of intercultural communication, about the state of formation of intercultural communicative competence of future English teachers in Adam Mickiewicz University. The research had been done in the form of a lecture, practical classes, questionnaire, small group discussions, conversation and test. The results of research conducted in Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan (Poland) among the undergraduates and bachelor students are presented in this work.

Keywords: *culture, intercultural communication, intercultural communicative competence, culture shock*

Introduction

Today, a lot of attention is paid to the study of foreign languages in educational institutions, because the world has long understood that knowledge of foreign languages gives a person an advantage over others who have not yet realized this. Therefore, it is important to throw all your efforts at solving the primary problems that entail a complete change in the fundamentals and requirements.

In this article we will discuss the state of formation of future English language teachers' intercultural communicative competence in Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan (Poland) and try to organize diagnostics of this competence formation.

It is now common knowledge that perceptions of appropriateness and politeness are culturally specific and can lead to a misunderstanding of intercultural communication. Accordingly, is it not worrying that most ESL/EFL courses do not provide students with enough information to avoid misunderstandings due to different cultural and linguistic backgrounds? Providing students with information about how language works (people understand what is being said, even if it is confusing because the literal meaning does not match the target meaning of the speaker) seems to be an important element of grammar [1]. The right to speak (how to apologize, how to refuse, etc.) and the teacher is not responsible for knowing the skills (which strategies and when to use). Decommunization is possible and useful, and, most importantly, it prepares students for the challenges of intercultural communication [2].

European citizens are a diverse group of people who, although different, do share a vast number of experiences, beliefs, behaviours, and who are characterised by emerging tendencies in the way in which they communicate. Europe, being in the process of becoming a diversified unit of intertwined cultures and languages, is no longer a set of individual, isolated countries protecting and securing solely their own interest. With the hopes of an even greater union between EU member states and the ideal of a plurilingual European,

fluent in intercultural communication, with European loyalty and ties to their roots, a need for action in European ELT classes is needed. It is no longer enough for people across Europe to learn English, since the English being taught and learnt is not one, but many [3].

With different Euro-Englishes being used (e.g. Polglish, Spanglish, etc.), intercultural communication is not made easy, but to the contrary, the variability creates obstacles where there should be none. Pragmatic transfer, being an integral part of language learning, influences the way L2 is used, and with speakers from different cultural backgrounds the probability of misunderstanding is large due to the possible lack of a common reference point to what is polite, appropriate and desirable linguistic and non-linguistic behaviour. Consistency, clarity and transparency of linguistic rules facilitate more effective communication, which is crucial for intercultural cooperation and the strengthening of ties between citizens of the member states.

It is evidently clear that intercultural communication is defined as situated communication between individuals or groups of different linguistic and cultural origins.

Researching the state of investigating the problems of formation of intercultural communicative competence of students in the Kazakhstani universities, comparing it with Asian and European Universities was the object of my investigation. And this article is the continuation of my research work. So, to do my research I came to Poland on my scientific internship of "Bolashak" program. Together with my scientific coordinator, PhD in Linguistics, professor of Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan - Aleksandra Wach, we had planned some research in intercultural communication.

On October, 10 in Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan I had conducted lecture "Bases on intercultural communication", tried to give the fundamentals and importance of intercultural communication in our society nowadays. Different videos and presentation on intercultural communication (further IC) were shown, later lots of issues on IC were discussed with students.

The undergraduates of the “English philology” educational program and the 3rd year bachelor students of “Linguistics” educational program were involved in the process of teaching and researching.

Next class was devoted to the fundamentals of intercultural communicative competence. A great attention was given to the students’ knowledge on intercultural communicative competence (further ICC), their opinion on the ways and methods of formation of ICC.

On November, 24, we have conducted survey among the students on the bases of intercultural communication and on the intercultural communicative competence fundamentals, students were active and tried to answer sincerely to all the questions, a question-answer work turned into the discussion, then an individual interview was taken among the students and at the end of the class a self test took place.

Research work on the formation of intercultural communicative competence of future English language teachers was conducted on the basis of “English philology” educational program – Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan.

22 future English language teachers took part in the experiment: one experimental group (10 students) and one control group (12 students). Research work was conducted during 3 months, in 2023-2024 academic year.

According to the questions of the survey lots of students gave a correct answer about the founders of “Intercultural communication” course. The result is given in the diagram 1.

Also, lots of students gave the full and correct answer interpreting the notion of “intercultural communication”. The most common answer was – a communication between two or more different representatives of various cultures The result is given in the diagram 2.

The results of the research of formation of motivational component of intercultural communicative competence of future English language teachers are presented in table 1.

Table 1.

Results of studying the level of formation of motivational component of intercultural communicative competence of future English language teachers

No	Levels	Students (%)
1	Low	36.8
2	Medium	53.9
3	High	9.3

Studying in a foreign country is an experience that we feel excitement, enthusiasm and a little bit of fear or adrenaline. However most of students go abroad unprepared for the meeting with a new culture and may experience psychological and physiological reactions which are called "culture shock". It occur in more or less intense and strike way but, everyone who travel are affected by it. Going through it and entering a phase of

cultural adaptation mean that you are now on the happy journey [4].

As for the question dealing with the culture shock, also most of the students gave a full and concrete answer as "a feeling of awkwardness because of the differences between native and foreign culture". The result is given in the diagram 3.

Coming to the conclusion it should be said that the state of formation of intercultural communicative competence of future English teachers in Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan (Poland) is in the process of improving and developing. The teachers of this University are in constant search of the effective ways and methods of students' intercultural communicative competence formation.

References:

1. Canale M. From communicative competence to communicative language pedagogy // *Language and Communication* / ed. by J. Richards & R. Schmidt. - London, Eng.: Longman; 1983. - p. 2-27.
2. Deardorff D.K. Identification and assessment of intercultural competence as a student outcome of internationalization // *Journal of Studies in Intercultural Education*. – 2006. - № 10. – p. 241-266.
3. Fantini A.E. -Exploring and Processing Intercultural Competence // *Sprogforum*. - 2003. - Vol. 6, No. 26. - p. 51-57.
4. Ter-Minasova S.G. Language and intercultural communication: studies. the manual. - M.: Slovo, 2000. – p.624